

Article

i-Game: Redefining Cultural Heritage Through Inclusive Game Design and Advanced Technologies

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Abstract: The intersection of serious games, advanced technologies, and culture offers new paths for fostering social inclusion and sustainability. This position paper presents i-Game, an EU project dedicated to transforming the relationship between cultural heritage and the gaming industry. By creating an open-source platform for inclusive game development, i-Game integrates tools such as Explainable AI (XAI) and virtual reality to enable diverse stakeholders—including underrepresented groups—to co-create games that address societal and cultural challenges. Through pilot projects in museums and the textile industry, i-Game explores the potential of gamification to enhance learning, creativity, and collaboration while advancing sustainable practices. The project highlights how interdisciplinary methodologies and ethical-design principles can reshape the cultural heritage landscape, democratizing access to innovative tools and fostering a deeper connection between technology and heritage.

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1. Introduction

The digital transformation of cultural heritage is reshaping how societies engage with their past, present, and future [1,2]. Digital technologies, such as artificial intelligence (AI), virtual reality (VR), and gamification, are playing an increasingly significant role in redefining interactions between cultural institutions and their audiences [3,4].

Cultural heritage institutions face significant challenges in attracting and engaging diverse audiences while adapting to rapidly evolving technological landscapes. Traditional methods of presentation often fail to captivate younger, digitally native generations, leading to a pressing need for innovative and interactive solutions. Gamification, defined as the application of game-design elements in non-gaming contexts, has been increasingly recognized as an effective approach to enhancing engagement and learning within cultural heritage settings [5]. Research suggests that serious games can contribute to knowledge retention, emotional connection to heritage, and the promotion of inclusivity by accommodating diverse learning preferences [6,7]. Museums and cultural institutions have begun embracing interactive storytelling and digital games to transform passive heritage

experiences into engaging learning opportunities, thereby making cultural heritage more accessible and appealing to broader audiences [8,9].

Digital games play an increasingly important role in cultural heritage applications, offering new ways to engage audiences and enhance learning experiences. As McGonigal (2011) argues, games can foster meaningful participation and address real-world challenges through engagement and collaboration [10]. Research also highlights their potential to improve cognitive skills and support creative problem-solving [11]. However, their integration in cultural heritage settings presents challenges related to accessibility, representation, and ethical design. AI-driven personalization and immersive technologies, for example, can enrich user experiences, but they also raise concerns about data privacy, inclusivity, and the potential for cultural misrepresentation. While some scholars emphasize AI's ability to enhance personalization, others caution against inherent biases that may distort cultural narratives [12]. Addressing these challenges is crucial to ensuring that digital games contribute meaningfully and ethically to cultural heritage preservation.

In addition to technological challenges, value co-creation and participatory design have gained prominence in recent years as critical elements of game development for cultural heritage. The inclusion of diverse stakeholders in the creative process fosters the development of meaningful cultural narratives that reflect multiple perspectives [13]. Research has shown that participatory design methodologies enhance the co-creation process by enabling cultural institutions, communities, and technology developers to collaborate effectively [14]. Studies in the field of serious games and heritage gamification have demonstrated the importance of collaboration in creating content that resonates with audiences while ensuring historical accuracy and cultural sensitivity [15].

Despite the evident potential of gamification, debates persist regarding its long-term impact and the extent to which it should be integrated into cultural heritage experiences. Some critics argue that gamification risks trivializing cultural content and reducing it to mere entertainment, while proponents emphasize its ability to foster deeper emotional and cognitive engagement [16]. The challenge lies in striking a balance between maintaining cultural authenticity and leveraging gamification to enhance visitor experiences. To address these concerns, i-Game integrates a participatory co-creation model that prioritizes cultural accuracy, ethical design, and accessibility. By involving diverse stakeholders—including cultural institutions, game developers, and end users through structured workshops and iterative feedback loops, i-Game will ensure that gamification enhances engagement without compromising the integrity of heritage content. Moreover, ethical considerations, such as ensuring accessibility for all users and respecting cultural sensitivities, remain paramount in the design and deployment of heritage games [17] and are also considered seriously in the context of the i-Game approach.

Overall, i-Game aims to address these challenges by providing an inclusive, open-source platform that empowers users to co-create culturally meaningful games. By integrating advanced technologies, such as AI and XAI (Explainable AI), and interdisciplinary approaches, the project seeks to bridge the gap between technological innovation and cultural heritage. The i-Game co-creation platform will facilitate collaboration between cultural institutions, technology developers, and community stakeholders. The result of this collaborative experience will be a Game Design Document (GDD), which will serve as the foundational blueprint for the development of cultural heritage games. This document will encapsulate core game mechanics, narrative structures, and accessibility considerations, ensuring that the resulting games are engaging, educational, and inclusive. In addition to the GDD, game developers will be equipped with AI/XAI and VR plugins developed within the project framework. These tools will enhance the realism, adaptiveness, and

accessibility of the games by enabling dynamic NPC behaviors, AI-assisted aesthetics, and immersive storytelling techniques.

As already mentioned, i-Game will also ensure that heritage games are designed to be accessible, ethical, and engaging for diverse audiences, including marginalized groups, such as people with disabilities, individuals with varying levels of technical skills, and different age and socio-cultural backgrounds. This approach aligns with the principles outlined in Article 30 of the UN Convention on the Rights of Persons with Disabilities, emphasizing the right to full participation in cultural life, recreation, leisure, and sport [18]. Through pilot initiatives in museums and the textile industry, i-Game will demonstrate how gamification can enhance learning, creativity, and collaboration while promoting sustainability [19].

In a nutshell, i-Game aspires (1) to engage video game stakeholders of different abilities, expertise, and disciplines and to contribute, learn, share, and tap into new innovative and economic opportunities; (2) to provide a collaborative platform with the tools to co-create mobile and virtual reality games by engaging different users from different backgrounds and sectors; (3) to develop an ethical-design culture in the video game industry; (4) to monitor, assess, and manage the impact that the video games have on different sectors, especially targeting culture/museums, creative industries, and fashion/textile; and (5) to help us understand why and how online games are positively impacting people, culture, and society and help extract the ingredients necessary for developing a new generation of games targeted to improve people's well-being.

This paper presents the project's vision and implementation strategies, situating it within the broader discourse on cultural heritage digitization and gamification. By drawing on the existing literature and analyzing the project's interdisciplinary approach, this work contributes to the ongoing discussion on how technology can enhance cultural engagement and sustainability. Although the project is still in its early stages, currently in the requirement analysis phase, substantial groundwork has already been laid. The project has conducted extensive desk and field research, engaging 158 stakeholders through interviews, focus groups, and surveys to define user needs and challenges in game co-creation. This has led to the identification of 27 high-level user requirements and the development of 15 user personas, which captures who the platform users will be; what their motivations and fears are; what their knowledge, skills, abilities, and interests are; etc., ensuring that the platform aligns with the needs of diverse stakeholders. Additionally, the i-Game project has defined a structured co-creation methodology, incorporating gamification and community-building strategies through dedicated workshops.

On a technical level, the project's impact monitoring dashboard has been established to track social, economic, and cultural outcomes in real time, aligning with global sustainability goals. Furthermore, a comprehensive legal and ethical analysis has been conducted, setting policy recommendations and regulatory guidelines for inclusive game development. The project has also defined the architecture of the co-creation platform, detailing its AI/XAI, VR, and collaborative tools to ensure accessibility and engagement. While empirical results and demonstrators are yet to come, these foundational efforts provide a robust starting point for redefining the relationship between cultural heritage and the gaming industry. The i-Game project represents an opportunity to establish novel pathways to inclusivity and innovation in digital cultural experiences.

2. Literature Review: Collaborative Platforms for Game Design

Collaborative game design platforms facilitate the co-creation of digital games by multiple users, including developers, designers, and end users. These platforms enable real-time interaction, version control, and accessibility for diverse stakeholders. The increasing

demand for inclusive and participatory design methodologies has led to the development of several co-creation tools aimed at enhancing engagement and democratizing game development [20].

Virtual sandbox environments such as Minecraft and Resonite (<https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Resonite>, accessed on 10 March 2025) provide a digital space where users collaboratively build and test game elements. Resonite, in particular, allows for real-time multi-user interactions in a persistent 3D space, enabling both synchronous and asynchronous co-creation of virtual worlds. Minecraft, on the other hand, has been used by Walsh et al. (2016) as a tool to support distributed co-design. This study highlights the importance of integrating virtual spaces into the game design process. By facilitating broader participation and creative expression among diverse user groups, these platforms align with the principles of participatory design and ensure that user input is embedded in the development pipeline [20].

PlayCanvas is an open-source WebGL game engine that supports multi-user, browser-based collaboration. It has been used for serious games, particularly in educational settings, to allow students and educators to co-design interactive experiences [21]. Its cloud-based infrastructure enables real-time updates, making it a useful tool for collaborative game development. However, it primarily focuses on the technical aspects of game creation rather than inclusive design methodologies [22].

Recent research has emphasized the role of participatory game design kits tailored for diverse user groups, including neurodiverse children. PartiPlay, a toolkit specifically designed for neurodiverse classrooms, promotes accessibility and inclusive game development through structured co-design processes [23]. Similarly, research on robotic game co-design demonstrates the importance of user-driven, adaptive methodologies in creating engaging and inclusive game environments [24].

The development of multiplayer games requires robust server architectures to facilitate seamless interaction between users. Research exploring the integration of Nakama with PlayCanvas has provided insights into how game developers can implement scalable and interactive co-design features in 3D games [22].

The i-Game platform distinguishes itself from existing collaborative game design tools in several key ways. Unlike general-purpose game design platforms, i-Game specifically focuses on cultural heritage preservation through interactive digital experiences. By leveraging XAI and virtual reality, the platform enables stakeholders to create games that promote historical and societal narratives. It prioritizes the co-creation of games by underrepresented and marginalized communities, ensuring that accessibility considerations are embedded in the development process. Unlike Resonite or PlayCanvas, which primarily serve general gaming audiences, i-Game incorporates universal design principles and ethical considerations from the outset.

The platform leverages AI for adaptive game balancing, NPC behavior modeling, and AI-assisted game design elements, making it more sophisticated than traditional sandbox environments. It fosters an open-source ecosystem, allowing for diverse stakeholders—including museums, educators, and independent developers—to contribute and refine gaming experiences collaboratively. Additionally, it integrates participatory design principles with AI and VR, ensuring that game creation aligns with the needs of cultural institutions and educational initiatives, a feature not emphasized in mainstream game design platforms.

Through these innovations, i-Game sets a new standard for inclusive and collaborative game design, ensuring that digital heritage experiences are engaging, ethical, and accessible to all.

3. Materials and Methods

The i-Game project adopted a comprehensive, interdisciplinary methodology (see Figure 1) integrating participatory design principles, co-creation strategies, and advanced technological solutions to foster inclusivity and sustainability in game development. The project followed an iterative and collaborative approach, ensuring that the developed platform and games aligned with the real needs of cultural and creative industries (CCSI) and society at large. At its core, the methodology was structured around three key phases: (1) requirement analysis and design, (2) development and co-creation, and (3) evaluation and impact assessment. Each phase was underpinned by well-defined processes leveraging state-of-the-art tools and frameworks to maximize engagement, creativity, and social impact. At this point, the project has completed the requirement analysis phase, as already stated in the introduction.

Figure 1. Methodology phases of the development and evaluation of the i-Game co-creation platform.

Each phase was underpinned by a set of well-defined processes that leveraged state-of-the-art tools and frameworks to maximize engagement, creativity, and social impact and is described in the following subsections.

3.1. Requirement Analysis and Design

The initial phase of the project focused on understanding the needs and challenges of stakeholders through targeted research and engagement strategies. A crucial aspect of this phase involved the identification and engagement of diverse stakeholders, such as museums, creative professionals, educators, and underrepresented groups, to capture their requirements and expectations. Through comprehensive content and need research, we analyzed cultural heritage challenges, gaming trends, and technological capabilities, leading to the definition of system architecture and user experience (UX) requirements. In addition, an inclusive design framework was employed to ensure accessibility and usability for users, with particular attention to marginalized groups. By considering these factors, such as diversity and equity, we will make sure that the outputs align with the principles of universal design and address the unique needs of various cultural heritage institutions.

3.2. Development of the Co-Creation Platform, AI, XAI, and VR Plugins

AI-powered algorithms enhance game realism and player satisfaction by enabling dynamic, adaptive behavior in game objects. Designers can integrate AI sophistication into objects, allowing them to exhibit intelligent behavior. AI in game development supports key functions such as the following:

- Pathfinding: Identifying the shortest route between points for character navigation.
- Character design: Creating engaging, lifelike characters.
- Game balance: Optimizing strategies to ensure fair competition among players.

AI-driven design patterns [25] have been successfully applied in educational and cultural heritage games, enhancing player engagement and realism. Notable examples include Assassin's Creed Discovery Tour, which leverages AI-driven NPC (Non-Player Character) behaviors to create historically accurate environments where users can explore interactive historical narratives. Similarly, serious games such as Mission US utilize AI for adaptive storytelling and personalized learning experiences. Building on these advancements, i-Game will develop reusable AI functionalities, including believable NPCs, player modeling, and adaptive game balancing, to enrich cultural heritage applications. Inspired by reusable game AI components [11], these tools will ensure historical accuracy, narrative coherence, and accessibility in gamified heritage experiences.

Traditional game AI has relied on decision trees, finite state machines, and pathfinding algorithms. Interpreting complex AI systems remains a challenge [26], particularly when used to control NPCs in games. Designers need ways to understand why an AI makes certain decisions to ensure fairness, predictability, and cultural sensitivity in historical and educational games. In i-Game, XAI helps developers and cultural institutions fine-tune AI-driven elements in a way that is both transparent and interpretable.

For example, when an AI-powered historical guide NPC reacts to a player's choices, XAI can clarify the following:

- General patterns in decision-making (e.g., how the NPC adapts its responses based on a player's interaction style).
- Specific actions (e.g., why an NPC highlights certain cultural artifacts over others).
- Adjustments based on fairness and inclusivity (e.g., preventing AI biases that could misrepresent historical events).

To achieve this, i-Game integrates adaptive AI techniques that go beyond traditional rule-based NPC behavior. Instead of following pre-scripted responses, NPCs will use deep learning and dynamic dialogue models (<https://github.com/undreamai/LLMUnity>, accessed on 10 March 2025) to react naturally. By leveraging Unity's ML-Agents toolkit, game developers can train intelligent, interactive characters, while AI-assisted game balance tools ensure fair and engaging gameplay experiences. Additionally, AI-generated visuals, supported by Stable Diffusion (<https://stablediffusion.com/tools>, accessed on 10 March 2025), help maintain historical accuracy in game environments. These explainability techniques ensure that game developers, can interpret, refine, and trust the AI's decisions, making heritage games both engaging and ethically sound.

To align visuals with creative intent, AI-generated content will be guided by text prompt creation and reference image collection, ensuring that aesthetic elements such as environments, character designs, and color schemes reflect user requirements and technical discussions. Therefore, XAI will further enhance transparency and usability by integrating feature importance analysis and surrogate models, allowing developers to better understand AI-driven behaviors. Advanced interpretability techniques such as LIME and SHAP (techniques to allow developers to monitor how difficulty levels evolve, preventing unfair challenges or unintended biases) will provide localized and global explanations,

making it easier to analyze AI-driven decisions in areas like NPC behavior and procedural content generation.

Following an agile, co-creation approach, i-Game will actively involve stakeholders through workshops and game jams, ensuring iterative refinement based on real-time feedback. MoSCoW [27] prioritization will structure development cycles efficiently, while research will also explore the automation of training agents for pathfinding, optimizing AI adaptability across various game environments. By integrating AI, XAI, and VR, i-Game fosters a collaborative, open-source ecosystem, advancing AI-driven game design while enriching cultural heritage experiences. A series of co-creation workshops and game jams further will enrich this process, offering opportunities for innovation and knowledge exchange among participants. These collaborative efforts not only facilitate the development of engaging cultural heritage games but also contribute to the building of a vibrant, inclusive community around the platform.

For that matter, we adopted the framework for inclusive design developed by the Inclusive Design Research Centre (IDRC) [28]. The guiding framework for inclusive design and innovation led to a methodology that has recognition of diversity, variability, and systemic complexity at its core. This inclusive approach supported organic growth and ensured fewer barriers for people across the full range of our society. The methodological approach proposed by IDRC is known as the ‘Virtuous Tornado’ (Figure 2).

Figure 2. The ‘Virtuous Tornado’.

The i-Game project applied a rigorous participatory design methodology, ensuring accessibility and inclusivity through direct engagement with diverse stakeholders. The platform will be designed with input from underrepresented groups, including persons with disabilities, minority communities, and individuals with varying levels of digital literacy. Through co-creation workshops, game jams, and structured participatory research, the project actively incorporates user feedback into game mechanics, UI/UX adjustments, and storytelling elements. To enhance accessibility, i-Game aligns with the European Accessibility Act and the WCAG 2.2 guidelines, ensuring that the platform's design will meet recognized international accessibility standards, making game co-creation tools more equitable and inclusive. More specifically, we will directly engage people from underrepresented groups (e.g., individuals with disabilities, marginalized communities, and those with limited digital literacy) through game jams, co-creation workshops, and participatory research sessions. The project's user analysis framework, developed until now through 158 stakeholder interviews, ensured, for instance, that the platform accounted for motivations, fears, and accessibility barriers of diverse participants.

The i-Game platform serves as a comprehensive and collaborative foundation for game design, integrating essential functionalities, features, and workflows that support a GDD while leveraging AI, XAI, and VR plugins. Designed to streamline game design, i-Game provides a structured environment where creativity, technology, and user experience converge.

In addition to the above technological resources (AI, XAI, and VR plugins), at its core, the platform incorporates multiple layers that work together seamlessly. The gamification layer enhances engagement through game mechanics, rewards, and motivational dynamics, while the storytelling layer facilitates narrative-driven co-creation. The aesthetical layer shapes the visual and artistic aspects of the game, ensuring cohesive and compelling game design, by using multimedia content of the museums involved in the gaming prototyping scenarios. The multimedia resource layer will provide access to rich multimedia assets sourced from museums and the fashion/textile industries, enriching the visual and thematic depth and relevance of games. Beyond content creation, the communication layer supports interaction, collaboration, and feedback mechanisms among co-creators, supporting the building of a colorful community. The platform also will ensure structured development with versioning and user role layers, offering role-based access and iterative game version management. By uniting open-source elements, i-Game transforms game development into an efficient, collaborative, and innovation-driven process, empowering creators to craft dynamic, visually stunning, and AI-enhanced educative gaming experiences.

3.3. Evaluation and Impact Assessment

The evaluation and impact assessment phase of the i-Game project is designed to measure the effectiveness and societal impact of the games developed using the i-Game platform. A comprehensive impact assessment framework has been established, combining both qualitative and quantitative evaluation methods to ensure a holistic understanding of the project's outcomes. A foundational step regards the identification of the project's key impact stakeholders, referred to as Target Groups (TGs). The identification of TGs was crucial, as it laid the groundwork for a more focused and relevant impact assessment, ensuring that the needs and expectations of all stakeholders were thoroughly understood and addressed (see Figure 3 below). As depicted in Figure 3, i-Game involves a diverse array of stakeholders, each playing a critical role in achieving the project's objectives. The stakeholder mapping process was meticulously detailed, linking each stakeholder to relevant outcomes and KPIs to ensure precise measurement and robust data collection. This approach laid a solid foundation for assessing the project's impact on various stakeholders,

fostering a comprehensive understanding of their contributions and benefits. The array of stakeholders was divided in five (5) clusters, each one retaining a number of related TGs. More specifically, we defined the following clusters:

Figure 3. Visual i-Game's impact stakeholders map.

Cluster 1 | Museums and cultural and creative industries (CCIs)

- Museums/CCIs institutions/professionals (TG1): These stakeholders are essential for integrating cultural elements into game development, thereby enhancing cultural preservation and innovation and increasing visitor experience and social innovation. Expected impacts include improved cultural engagement and the adoption of advanced technological solutions in preserving cultural heritage and making it more approachable.
- Museums/CCIs visitors/customers (TG2): Visitors and customers will benefit from enriched cultural experiences through gamified interactions, leading to increased cultural literacy, engagement, and sense of cultural belonging and well-being.

Cluster 2 | Textile and fashion

- Textile and fashion industry/professionals (TG3): This group will experience enhanced creativity and innovation in cultural services and products, improving sustainability and integrating cultural and gamified narratives into fashion design.

- Textile and Fashion customers (TG4): Customers will have greater access to innovative, sustainable fashion products enriched by cultural elements, promoting cultural appreciation and sustainable consumption and enhancing their own creativity.

Cluster 3 | End users

- Game players (TG5): As primary beneficiaries, game players will enjoy enhanced gaming experiences that are culturally enriched and educational, fostering broader cultural awareness and knowledge.
- Game co-creators (TG6): Co-creators will benefit from collaborative opportunities, enhancing their creative and technical skills through participation in game development processes and create a sense of belonging also for underrepresented groups.

Cluster 4 | Game industry

- Game industry (TG7): Industry stakeholders will see advancements in technology and innovation, promoting ethical practices and sustainable growth within the industry.

Cluster 5 | Wider society

- Citizens (TG8): The broader public will experience increased cultural engagement and participation in community activities, fostering social cohesion and a sense of belonging.
- Policy makers (TG9): Policy makers will be equipped with insights from the project's outcomes, aiding in the development of policies that support innovation, cultural preservation, and sustainability.
- SMEs (TG10): Small and medium enterprises will benefit from enhanced networking opportunities, resource sharing, and economic growth through participation in innovative projects.
- Higher education and research institutions (TG11): These institutions will gain from enhanced knowledge exchange and collaborative research opportunities, fostering academic and practical advancements.
- Social economy organizations (TG12): SEOs will benefit from increased awareness and integration of sustainability and inclusiveness practices, promoting social equity and innovative solutions.

One of the core methodologies utilized is the Social Return on Investment (SROI), which quantifies social, cultural, and economic impact in monetary terms, offering a structured approach to assessing the broader value of i-Game. At this stage, the project has conducted a preliminary analysis, identifying key impact areas and relevant financial proxies, which will later be used to calculate the SROI ratio. While specific financial values have not yet been assigned, this preparatory work ensures that the methodology is ready for implementation in the later phases of the project.

Additionally, the i-Game project integrates a real-time impact monitoring dashboard, powered by Microsoft Power BI (<https://www.microsoft.com/en-us/power-platform/products/power-bi>, accessed on 10 March 2025), to track and visualize Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) across social, economic, and cultural domains. This dashboard allows stakeholders to continuously monitor and adjust strategies based on collected data. Alongside SROI, the project employs the Theory of Change (ToC) framework, which maps long-term impact pathways and ensures that the project's objectives align with its expected societal contributions.

More specifically, the i-Game impact assessment follows a structured approach that aligns project activities with defined outcome areas, each linked to measurable indicators. Figure 4 (see below) describes these outcome areas, followed by their corresponding KPIs and the planned data collection method (see Tables 1–7).

#	Outcome Area	#	Outcome
1	Knowledge Exchange	1.1	Expanded knowledge on arts and culture
		1.2	Expanded knowledge on technology development
2	Network Development	2.1	Enhanced network development
		2.2	Enhanced cross-sectoral collaboration
3	Community and Social Relationships	3.1	Strengthened sense of belonging to a broader community
		3.2	Increased participation in cultural activities
4	Economic development	4.1	Increased job opportunities
		4.2	Boosted organisations sustainability
		4.3	Innovation in cultural services and products
5	Learning & capacity building	5.1	Development of soft and life skills
		5.2	Improved educational performance/experience
		5.3	Enhancement of hard skills
6	Social inclusiveness	6.1	Elevated awareness on sustainability and inclusion
		6.2	Increased accessibility to cultural initiatives
7	Technological development	7.1	Human-centred technology development
		7.2	Fostered legal awareness and ethical-design culture in video game industry

Figure 4. An outline of the high-level framework with outcome areas and specific outcomes.

Table 1. KPIs for Outcome Area 1/knowledge exchange, with relevant data collection method.

#	KPI	Data Collection Method
1	Percentage of end users reporting increased knowledge on arts and culture after project activities	Surveys
2	Percentage of cultural institutions reporting improved knowledge exchange and preservation practices	Interviews and feedback forms
3	Number of empowered professionals understanding culture- and fashion-related issues in game development	Surveys and interviews with professionals
4	Number of stakeholders claiming improved sensitivity and awareness of cultural content	Surveys and focus groups
5	Percentage of cultural institutions/museum administrators reporting new knowledge on creating cultural experiences and narratives	Surveys
6	Number of empowered professionals understanding tech-related issues in game development	Workshops and training evaluations
7	Number of cultural and textile/fashion organizations reporting enhanced knowledge on gaming and tech sectors	Surveys and interviews with organizations
8	Number of empowered professionals understanding more about tech-related issues related to technology development	Workshops and training evaluations

Table 2. KPIs for Outcome Area 2/network development, with relevant data collection method.

#	KPI	Data Collection Method
10	Number of organizations engaged and degree of engagement	Membership records and participation logs
11	Number of stakeholders and end users actively involved in network development initiatives	Surveys and participation records
12	Number of new partnerships formed	Partnership agreements
13	Number of initiatives and projects launched from new partnerships	Project reports and case studies
14	Number of cross-sectoral collaborations resulting in new cultural products or services	Surveys and interviews
15	Number of cross-sectoral participants actively engaging in co-design activities on the platform	Participation logs and activity records
16	Number of stakeholders reporting enhanced collaboration and understanding with other stakeholders from diverse sectors	Surveys and interviews with stakeholders
17	Number of co-design initiatives and projects initiated within the platform by cross-sectoral community members	Platform analytics and project reports

Table 3. KPIs for Outcome Area 3/community and social relationships, with relevant data collection method.

#	KPI	Data Collection Method
18	Percentage of end users reporting improved sense of belonging to the local community through heritage promotion	Surveys and community feedback
19	Percentage of community members reporting a stronger sense of identity and belonging to the gaming community	Surveys and community feedback
20	Number of end users actively participating in community events	Event participation logs
21	Number of community-driven initiatives supported by the project	Community project reports
22	Percentage increase in participation in cultural activities	Attendance records and surveys
23	Number of new end users visiting partner cultural institutions for the first time during or after the project	Visitor logs and feedback forms
24	Number of end users expressing a desire to participate in future cultural activities	Surveys and focus groups

Table 4. KPIs for Outcome Area 4/economic development, with relevant data collection method.

#	KPI	Data Collection Method
25	Percentage of stakeholder organizations developing job descriptions for new roles inspired by the project's outcomes	Analysis of job postings and organizational reports
26	Number of stakeholders planning to recruit or expand their workforce due to project-inspired initiatives	Surveys and focus groups with stakeholders
27	New funding/investments attracted by cultural institutions and fashion designers/textile companies for sustainable products	Financial records
28	Number of organizations reporting improved sustainability practices	Sustainability assessments
29	Number of new services launched and innovated	Innovation logs and project reports
30	Number of newly created or innovated products	Product logs, innovation records, and surveys
31	Number of good practices disseminated	Best practices documentation

Table 5. KPIs for Outcome Area 5/learning and capacity building, with relevant data collection method.

#	KPI	Data Collection Method
32	Number of people reporting increased soft and life skills through project activities	Surveys and interviews
33	Number of people reporting improved educational performance through digital experiences	Academic records and surveys
34	Number of fashion/textile professionals reporting enhanced technical skills in gamification and transmedia storytelling due to the project's activities	Surveys and interviews with fashion/textile professionals
35	Number of cultural industry professionals reporting enhanced technical skills in service innovation and experience management through gamified experiences	Surveys and interviews with cultural industry professionals
36	Number of game co-designers reporting enhanced technical skills in game design and technology development through the co-design platform	Surveys and interviews with game co-designers
37	Number of contents/technical knowledge consumed during the game design process	Content usage analytics
38	Number of end users claiming improved work efficiency thanks to the development of hard skills	Surveys and interviews

Table 6. KPIs for Outcome Area 6/social inclusiveness, with relevant data collection method.

#	KPI	Data Collection Method
39	Number of end users reporting increased sensitivity to sustainability and social inclusion issues	Surveys and interviews
40	Number of stakeholders claiming to have reached a deeper understanding of social inclusivity and its value through gamification	Focus groups and surveys
41	Number of end users with vulnerable and/or disadvantaged conditions claiming greater inclusion and accessibility in cultural experiences delivered through video games and other project-promoted activities	Surveys and interviews with end users

For instance, Table 1 presents KPIs for Outcome Area 1, which is related to “Knowledge exchange”, and links these KPIs to the foreseen data collection methods. This structured presentation was followed for all other outcome areas in the following Tables 2–7 in order to ensure a thorough understanding and facilitate future monitoring and effective evaluation.

Moving forward, the next phases will involve systematic data collection from pilot projects in museums and the cultural sector, followed by the validation of financial proxies and monetization-based assessments. Financial proxies (see Table 8) are not static and can be adapted during the project lifecycle. As research progresses and new data become available, proxies can be refined or replaced with more accurate or relevant alternatives. This flexibility ensures that the SROI calculation remains robust and reflective of the true value generated by the project. Continuous monitoring and periodic reviews of financial proxies, guided by stakeholder feedback and emerging best practices, allow the i-Game project to maintain high standards of accuracy and relevance in its impact assessment. This adaptive approach ensures the financial proxies stay aligned with the project's evolving understanding of its impacts. The aforementioned efforts will provide scientific evidence of i-Game's impact, ensuring that the findings contribute to policy recommendations, sustainable business models, and best practices in heritage gamification.

Table 7. KPIs for Outcome Area 7/technological development, with relevant data collection method.

#	KPI	Data Collection Method
42	Number of digitized cultural objects and assets	Digitalization logs and reports
43	Percentage of platform users reporting satisfaction with the accessibility features	Surveys and feedback forms
44	Number of collaborative projects initiated through the platform	Platform analytics and project logs
45	Percentage of users who understand and effectively use explainable AI components	Surveys and usage analytics
46	Number of users participating in workshops on ethics and social inclusiveness	Workshop attendance logs
47	User engagement levels in co-design activities on the platform	Platform analytics (e.g., time spent, actions taken)
48	Percentage of gamified experiences co-designed on the platform that include elements of diversity and inclusion	Content analysis of co-designed projects
49	Number of users participating in workshops on heritage promotion and education through gamification	Workshop attendance logs
50	Percentage of platform users who feel their contributions to co-design activities are valued	Surveys and feedback forms
51	Number of new features implemented on the platform based on user feedback	Platform development logs and user feedback analysis
52	Percentage of users who report increased knowledge of ethics, diversity, and inclusion after using the platform	Surveys and interviews with users
53	Number of video game professionals reporting participation in legal awareness programs	Surveys and interviews with professionals
54	Number of video game companies and SMEs adopting legal compliance frameworks	Surveys and interviews with companies
55	Number of legal awareness materials (e.g., guidelines, toolkits) disseminated to video game professionals	Distribution logs and feedback forms
56	Number of video game professionals reporting participation in ethical-design culture programs	Surveys and interviews with professionals
57	Number of ethical-design guidelines and best practices disseminated to video game professionals	Distribution logs and feedback forms
58	Number of video game companies adopting ethical-design practices	Surveys and interviews with companies

Table 8. Cashable KPI i-Game with relevant financial proxy description (color-coded as per the scheme introduced earlier for clarity).

KPI#	KPI	Target Value	Proxy Description
3	Number of empowered professionals understanding culture- and fashion-related issues in game development	100 professionals	Course on Digital Humanities
6	Number of empowered professionals understanding tech-related issues in game development	60% of professionals (60 out of 100)	Course on Digital Humanities
7	Number of cultural and textile/fashion organizations reporting enhanced knowledge on gaming and tech sectors	50 organizations	Course on Digital Humanities
8	Number of empowered professionals understanding more about tech-related issues related to technology development	50% of professionals (250 out of 500)	Course on Digital Humanities

Table 8. Cont.

KPI#	KPI	Target Value	Proxy Description
11	Number of new partnerships formed	10 partnerships/year	Average value of new partnership deals
12	Number of initiatives and projects launched from new partnerships	5 projects/year	Average costs of urban regeneration interventions and territorial animation projects
13	Number of cross-sectoral collaborations resulting in new cultural products or services	12 collaborations/year	Tutoring cost for a incubation process
19	Number of end users actively participating in community events	1000 end users	Value of event participation fees
21	Percentage increase in participation in cultural activities	50% increase (250 additional participants out of 500)	Increased revenue from ticket sales
25	Number of stakeholders planning to recruit or expand their workforce due to project-inspired initiatives	15 stakeholders	Annual unemployment benefit
26	New funding/investments attracted by cultural institutions and fashion designers/textile companies for sustainable products	7 funding granted	Tuscany region financing to cultural organizations through public call
28	Number of new services launched and innovated	12 services/year	Tutoring cost for a incubation process
29	Number of newly created or innovated products	30 products	Tutoring cost for a incubation process
31	Number of people reporting increased soft and life skills through project activities	50% of participants (250 out of 500)	Soft skills course—Forma Camere, Camera di Commercio di Roma
33	Number of fashion/textile professionals reporting enhanced technical skills in gamification and transmedia storytelling due to the project's activities	60 professionals	Cost of game design course
34	Number of cultural industry professionals reporting enhanced technical skills in service innovation and experience management through gamified experiences	50 professionals	Cost of innovation management course
35	Number of game co-designers reporting enhanced technical skills in game design and technology development through the co-design platform	80 co-designers	Cost of game design course
41	Number of digitized cultural objects and assets	350 digitized objects	Cost savings from digital preservation
43	Number of collaborative projects initiated through the platform	20 projects/year	Cost of digitalization voucher
45	Number of users participating in workshops on ethics and social inclusiveness	200 users/year	Course on Digital Humanities
50	Number of new features implemented on the platform based on user feedback	10 features/year	Development cost savings per feature
52	Number of video game professionals reporting participation in legal awareness programs	150 professionals/year	Average cost of legal awareness training program per professional
53	Number of video game companies and SMEs adopting legal compliance frameworks	40 companies	Cost of implementing a legal compliance framework per company

Table 8. Cont.

KPI#	KPI	Target Value	Proxy Description
54	Number of legal awareness materials (e.g., guidelines, toolkits) disseminated to video game professionals	500 materials/year	Cost of producing and distributing legal awareness materials per unit
55	Number of video game professionals reporting participation in ethical-design culture programs	200 professionals/year	Average cost of ethical-design training program per professional
56	Number of ethical-design guidelines and best practices disseminated to video game professionals	300 materials/year	Cost of producing and distributing ethical-design materials per unit

The games developed within the project underwent testing and evaluation in three key locations—the Estonian National Museum (ENM), the Museo del Tessuto in Prato (TMP), and the fashion and textile local ecosystem in Central Macedonia, allowing for a comprehensive assessment of their effectiveness in engaging audiences and addressing sustainability challenges. To facilitate continuous improvement, the project also will implement an impact-monitoring dashboard that provides real-time data on project outcomes, user engagement, and feedback. The description of the three test scenarios follows.

3.3.1. Exploring Textile Heritage, Sustainability, and Urban Memory Through Gamified Experiences

Museums are increasingly embracing video games to offer more interactive and educational experiences, extending their reach, enhancing monetization opportunities, and fostering collaboration. Beyond entertainment, video games have emerged as powerful tools for educating audiences about art, history, and cultural heritage [29]. However, successful integration requires addressing key challenges, including aligning game design with educational objectives, securing funding for development and maintenance, and strengthening partnerships between museums and the gaming industry [2]. Overcoming these hurdles is essential to supporting the digital transformation of museums, fostering digitally literate leadership, and bridging the digital divide [30].

In response to these challenges, the ENM is launching a pilot initiative aimed at developing game prototypes that seamlessly integrate with its exhibitions and broader projects. This effort will bring together museum curators, researchers, game designers, and industry experts to explore how digital games can translate complex themes of textile sustainability into interactive experiences [31].

One focus of the pilot involves the development of a video game centered on textile sustainability, inspired by interdisciplinary research on traditional dyeing practices. This initiative will allow audiences to explore the influence of historical techniques on modern and future textile industries, the role of dyes in sustainability and well-being, and the socio-cultural significance of textile colors [32]. Additionally, the collaboration between curators, researchers, and exhibition staff will be studied to better understand the co-creation process and stakeholder engagement [33]. Another facet of the scenario could be to engage museum visitors through a gamified exhibit that explores the future of textiles by highlighting sustainability, innovation, and traditional craft knowledge. The game will take audiences on a journey through the lifecycle of textiles, from home-based craftsmanship to industrial production and recycling practices [34]. Players will navigate sustainability challenges such as circular design, textile waste reduction, and the integration of smart textiles into modern fashion [35]. By combining storytelling with interactive gameplay, the exhibit encourages critical engagement with sustainability issues while showcasing the continuing relevance of traditional textile practices. The pilot will also assess the

collaboration process among stakeholders and the museum's readiness to incorporate gamified learning experiences [36].

The exploration of urban heritage through gamification extends beyond the museum walls, immersing audiences in a narrative-driven digital reconstruction of a former military airport with Cold War-era significance. This initiative will leverage VR technology to offer an interactive, first-person exploration of the site's historical evolution, transforming its ruins into a living archive where visitors can engage with different moments in time [37]. Stepping into the virtual space, users will move through historically reconstructed environments, encountering key locations, events, and figures that shaped the site's role during the Cold War. Interactive hotspots will allow players to examine declassified documents, listen to oral histories, and manipulate reconstructed objects, gaining insight into the geopolitical tensions, surveillance practices, and technological advancements of the era. The experience will be structured as a historical investigation, where players adopt different roles—such as journalists, historians, or local witnesses—and navigate branching narratives based on their research decisions [38].

Together, these initiatives illustrate how digital innovation and gamification can enhance cultural engagement, promote sustainability, and encourage collaboration across diverse sectors. The ENM's approach offers a forward-thinking model for cultural institutions seeking to embrace digital tools and transform museum experiences for contemporary audiences [39].

3.3.2. Gamifying Sustainability and Circular Consumption

The integration of gamification and digital tools into cultural institutions is revolutionizing audience engagement, transforming cultural exploration into an interactive and immersive experience that fosters deeper connections and learning [40]. The TMP through the i-Game seeks to capitalize on gamification to tackle key challenges within the textile and fashion sectors, with a strong focus on sustainability and circular consumption [41]. Positioned as a hub for piloting the i-Game approach, the TMP aims to activate the local textile industry ecosystem, deeply embedded in regional traditions and identified as a strategic priority within Tuscany's Smart Specialization Strategy. At the heart of this initiative is the goal of enhancing the museum's appeal to broader audiences, particularly younger generations, by offering engaging and interactive educational experiences. Through the co-creation of games, participants will explore sustainable practices within the textile and clothing industries, drawing on the museum's rich physical and digitized collections. These gamified experiences will cover crucial topics such as the lifecycle of textile products, the influence of consumer habits, sustainable business models, and the critical role of labeling and traceability in fostering ethical consumption. In alignment with the European Union's new Textile Strategy, the pilot ensures relevance to contemporary policy frameworks, providing an up-to-date, thought-provoking exploration of sustainability challenges in the sector.

This endeavor will involve a diverse array of stakeholders, including museum visitors, cultural professionals, students, local associations, and industry experts, fostering an environment of collaborative game development. By tapping into the collective expertise of these groups, the Textile Museum aims to co-create societal value while addressing pressing industry challenges. The co-creation process is envisioned as a dynamic and inclusive space for dialogue, innovation, and education, empowering participants to shape sustainable solutions rooted in the museum's heritage and cultural assets.

A primary objective of the pilot is to educate younger generations about sustainable and circular consumption patterns, leveraging gamification as an experiential learning tool to simplify complex topics and promote responsible consumer behavior [42]. Game formats such as treasure hunts, escape games, and virtual pathways will challenge par-

ticipants to make sustainable decisions, bridging the gap between theory and practice in an engaging manner [2]. Given their pivotal role in shaping future consumption habits and their affinity for digital experiences, the younger demographic is at the forefront of the initiative, aligning with the rising demand for interactive educational content tailored to their preferences [43]. Partnerships play a crucial role in ensuring the project's success, with students specializing in fashion and textile studies acting as key co-creators and test users, providing valuable feedback on game mechanics and relevance. Collaborations with digital design schools and gamification start-ups will further enhance the development of cost-effective and impactful solutions. This cross-sectoral collaboration highlights the transformative potential of gamification in addressing complex societal challenges and fostering sustainable innovation [44].

Ultimately, the TMP pilot stands as a testament to the power of gamification as an innovative tool for cultural institutions to bridge the gap between education and entertainment [45]. By blending traditional curatorial practices with interactive, immersive experiences, the project not only reinforces the museum's cultural role but also contributes to shaping a sustainable future for the textile and fashion industries. Furthermore, the i-GAME pilot underscores the critical link between innovation and collaboration, emphasizing the importance of cultural institutions in driving meaningful change within their communities [46].

3.3.3. Driving Digital Innovation and Sustainability in Central Macedonia's Textile Industry Through Digital Games

This scenario focused on utilizing digital innovation and co-creation methodologies to address critical challenges within the fashion and textile industry in Central Macedonia. This initiative engaged a diverse network of stakeholders, including public authorities, academic institutions, designers, textile companies, and researchers, to collaboratively design and develop gamified solutions using the i-Game platform. By leveraging cutting-edge technologies and fostering cross-sector collaboration, the pilot aimed to drive innovation, promote sustainability, and enhance the regional textile ecosystem.

The fashion and textile sector in Central Macedonia faces significant challenges, including the need for greater sustainability, digital transformation, and enhanced collaboration among stakeholders. The industry must adapt to shifting consumer expectations and increasing demands for transparency and accountability, particularly concerning environmental impact. According to the provided resources, VR can revolutionize consumer engagement by offering immersive experiences, such as virtual garment try-ons and interactive design visualizations. Studies demonstrate that these technologies not only improve user satisfaction but also reduce environmental impact by minimizing the need for physical prototypes (Donatiello et al., 2018; Papadopoulos et al., 2022) [31,32].

The pilot seeks to engage at least ten stakeholder organizations in co-design workshops to identify key challenges and develop innovative game prototypes tailored to the sector's needs. This participatory approach is informed by insights from the provided desk research, which highlights the importance of fostering collaboration between diverse actors to achieve effective solutions. For instance, the inclusion of tools like deep-learning-based garment classification can streamline production processes and improve product categorization, as demonstrated by recent advancements in machine learning [32]. These insights underscore the transformative potential of integrating advanced technologies into the fashion and textile ecosystem.

3.4. Ethical Considerations and Open Science

Ethical-design principles are deeply embedded in the project to ensure responsible data usage and inclusivity. i-Game adheres to stringent guidelines related to intellectual

property (IP), data privacy, and ethical game design, fostering a culture of responsible innovation that respects the rights and interests of all stakeholders. Open science practices were embraced throughout the project, with public access provided to datasets, methodologies, and findings. This commitment to transparency and reproducibility not only enhanced the credibility of the project but also enabled a wider community of researchers and practitioners to benefit from its insights by maintaining high ethical standards and promoting open access.

4. Discussion

The i-Game project is at a pivotal stage, having completed the requirement analysis phase and laid the groundwork for its next steps. Over the past year, the project has engaged 158 stakeholders, conducted interviews, focus groups, and surveys and defined 27 high-level user requirements and 15 user personas to ensure that the platform aligns with the needs of cultural institutions, game developers, and diverse communities. Additionally, a structured co-creation methodology has been established, incorporating gamification and community-building strategies to facilitate inclusive and participatory game design. While the project's progress has been considerable, several key considerations will shape the upcoming development phase. One critical aspect is ensuring that the transition from theoretical frameworks to functional prototypes effectively integrates stakeholder feedback. The diversity of stakeholders, from museum curators to game designers and game developers, presents both an opportunity and a challenge, as balancing technical innovation with cultural sensitivity requires continuous dialogue and iteration.

The architecture of the co-creation platform has been defined, incorporating AI/XAI, VR, and accessibility features, yet the practical implementation and user testing of these components remain a key focus for the next phase. The project's impact monitoring dashboard has been developed to track social, economic, and cultural outcomes, providing a data-driven foundation for assessing long-term impact. However, ensuring that these impact assessment tools effectively capture the diverse ways in which gamification enhances cultural heritage engagement will require further refinement as empirical results emerge.

Looking forward, the main challenge will be validating the methodologies and tools in real-world settings. The pilot initiatives in museums and the textile industry will serve as a testing ground for the platform's capabilities, providing insights into how different user groups interact with the co-creation framework. Moreover, as the project progresses toward developing demonstrators, key questions around sustainability, adoption by cultural institutions, and the ethical considerations of AI-driven personalization will become increasingly relevant.

Designed with inclusivity at its core, the platform will adhere to WCAG 2.2 (<https://www.w3.org/TR/WCAG22/>, accessed on 10 March 2025) Level AA compliance, enabling users of various abilities and backgrounds to engage effectively. Additionally, it aligns with the principles of the European Accessibility Act [47], reinforcing the commitment to removing digital barriers and ensuring equal access to cultural participation. This approach is further supported by EU policies advocating for the right of people with disabilities [48] to engage fully in cultural life, as highlighted by the European Parliament. Additionally, stakeholder engagement will be a critical component, with more than 300 cross-sector professionals, including game designers, educators, and museum curators, actively participating in focus groups until now that have refined user needs for platform usability and have been translated to technical requirements.

As the project transitions from the requirement analysis phase to the development and implementation phase, efforts will focus on refining the co-creation platform, integrating AI-driven features, and validating methodologies through pilot initiatives. Over

the next twelve months, the primary focus will be on developing and refining the core functionalities of the platform, ensuring that it effectively supports stakeholder interaction and accessibility. Particular attention will be given to implementing the AI/XAI modules, which will enhance adaptive game mechanics and explainable AI-driven decision-making. This is an important methodological contribution of this study, viz. the advancement of AI-driven cultural heritage gamification by integrating XAI and participatory co-creation methodologies. Unlike previous approaches that rely on opaque AI models, i-Game will enhance transparency in game mechanics and NPC decision-making through SHAP, LIME, and surrogate modeling techniques. These advancements will make AI-powered game storytelling interpretable and ethically sound, preventing misrepresentation in digital heritage experiences.

Furthermore, this study addresses a critical gap in inclusive game development by empowering underrepresented communities to actively shape game narratives. Through iterative co-creation workshops, persona-driven accessibility testing, and multimodal interaction features, i-Game will foster a democratized approach to game design, ensuring that digital cultural heritage remains accessible to diverse stakeholders across different abilities and cultural backgrounds. Additionally, usability and accessibility features will be further developed in alignment with universal design principles and the European Accessibility Act. Internal testing and iterative refinement cycles will also be conducted, incorporating feedback from early adopters within cultural institutions to improve user experience and platform functionality.

Following this, the project will enter a pilot phase in three key locations: the Estonian National Museum, the Museo del Tessuto, and the Central Macedonia textile industry sector. These pilot studies will play a crucial role in validating the methodologies and co-creation capabilities of the platform in real-world settings. They will assess how different user groups interact with the system, evaluate the effectiveness of participatory co-creation strategies, and measure the impact of gamified experiences on engagement with cultural heritage. The lessons drawn from these pilots will inform further refinements, ensuring that the platform is adaptable to diverse cultural and institutional needs.

Alongside these technical and methodological developments, the project will continue to expand its network of industry professionals, educators, and policymakers, strengthening cross-sector collaborations and fostering a broader adoption of gamified strategies in cultural heritage. A series of workshops, training sessions, and game jams will be organized to equip cultural institutions with the necessary skills and knowledge to integrate these tools into their existing practices. This hands-on engagement with stakeholders will help bridge the gap between theoretical innovation and practical implementation.

In parallel, the project's impact assessment framework will be fully operationalized, leveraging both the Social Return on Investment (SROI) and Theory of Change (ToC) methodologies to systematically measure societal, cultural, and economic benefits. The impact monitoring dashboard will provide real-time data to track engagement levels, adoption rates, and the overall effectiveness of game-based learning interventions. These assessment tools will ensure that the project remains responsive to stakeholder needs while also providing empirical evidence of its impact.

As i-Game progresses toward its final stages, efforts will shift toward policy recommendations and long-term sustainability. Best-practice guidelines and policy briefs will be developed to facilitate the broader adoption of gamification in cultural heritage institutions, ensuring that the project's findings contribute meaningfully to the field. Dissemination strategies will include academic publications, presentations at international conferences, and direct engagement with European policymakers to integrate the project's innovations into broader cultural and creative industry policies. Through this structured roadmap,

i-Game will evolve from a research-driven framework into a fully functional and scalable model, demonstrating how gamification can transform cultural heritage engagement in a lasting and impactful way.

Future research will focus on advancing XAI methodologies in game design to enhance transparency, user trust, and engagement. Key directions include refining XAI techniques to deliver more intuitive, real-time feedback to designers; enabling adaptive AI-driven narratives that dynamically respond to player choices while ensuring interpretability; and examining user perceptions of AI-driven decision-making within game environments. A crucial area of exploration will be the ethical implications of XAI in cultural heritage games, particularly bias mitigation in AI-generated narratives and balancing authenticity with AI-driven content generation. Additionally, improving multimodal AI explanations—integrating visual, textual, and interactive elements—will provide developers with deeper insights into AI-driven behaviors. Further advancements will involve refining feature attribution techniques such as LIME [13] and SHAP [49] for game environments, allowing for more precise control over AI-driven difficulty balancing and procedural content generation. The integration of neurosymbolic AI, combining deep learning with symbolic reasoning, offers another promising avenue for enhancing the interpretability of AI decision-making in complex, narrative-driven games.

A key technical challenge is the generalization and automation of training agents for pathfinding in games, particularly within frameworks like Unity. Automating this process could significantly streamline AI development, making adaptive in-game behaviors more scalable and accessible to designers. These research efforts will contribute to more transparent, engaging, and accessible AI-driven gaming experiences, ultimately benefiting both developers and players across diverse gaming contexts.

Finally, despite the lack of empirical data at this stage, the research presented in this article makes a significant contribution by laying the foundation for future technological innovations in cultural heritage gamification using a co-creation platform as a platform for the production of a Game Design Document. The integration of AI, participatory design, and impact-driven methodologies positions i-Game as a novel approach, offering a transparent, replicable framework for digital game co-creation in cultural heritage contexts. We believe this manuscript will be valuable to researchers and practitioners alike, fostering dialogue and collaboration in the interdisciplinary space of electronics, computer science, and heritage preservation.

5. Conclusions

The i-Game project represents an innovative approach to integrating AI, XAI, VR, gamification, and cultural heritage, fostering an inclusive and participatory game development ecosystem. By combining co-creation methodologies enhanced with AI, the project establishes a technologically advanced and ethically responsible framework for digital heritage applications. The development of an open-source platform ensures accessibility for a diverse range of stakeholders, including museum professionals, game developers, educators, and underrepresented communities.

While still in its early stages, i-Game has already achieved significant milestones, including the definition of high-level user requirements and the design of an interdisciplinary co-creation methodology. The project's pilot initiatives in museums and the textile industry further demonstrate the potential of gamified experiences in promoting learning, creativity, and cultural engagement.

As the project progresses, future efforts will focus on refining AI-driven decision-making tools, enhancing accessibility through compliance with the European Accessibility Act and WCAG 2.2 standards, and evaluating the platform's impact through the Social

Return on Investment (SROI) and Theory of Change (ToC) methodologies. These next steps will ensure that i-Game not only advances the technical frontiers of heritage-focused gamification but also provides a scalable and sustainable model for interdisciplinary collaboration in the cultural sector.

By bridging the gap between technology and cultural heritage, the i-Game project lays the foundation for new paradigms in digital preservation and interactive storytelling. Its contributions extend beyond the scope of a single research initiative, offering a replicable and adaptable framework that can inspire future applications in education, public engagement, and cultural policy development.

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